

THEORETICAL APPROACHES TO CREATION OF PEDAGOGICAL CONCEPTS

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Abstract: *This article presents theoretical approaches to the creation of pedagogical concepts of the concept of implementation based on certain rules in the use of modern methods of teaching students in higher education institutions.*

Key words: *Pedagogy, system, methodology, approach, electronic education, concept, individual education, digital education, rule, direction, culture.*

INTRODUCTION

The basis for the practical implementation of the Basic Rules of digital education as a pedagogical system, the creation and development of its methodology and didactics are pedagogical approaches, the effectiveness of which is assessed in three main positions: from the point of view of coordination of the content of the pedagogical approach with the historiography of the problem under study, practical significance for public use, that is, the adaptation of the content of the concept to modern educational conditions, is carried out in terms of the possibility of obtaining the desired results using it.

Education originated with the emergence of human society and has existed throughout its history, fulfilling from the beginning the general function of transferring social experience from generation to Generation.

METHODS

The most important elements of social experience are all the data collected by mankind about the world and methods of performing various types of activities, as well as the experience of their implementation, including a system of general intellectual and practical skills and abilities, that is, objectified knowledge, experience. Mastering social experience for an individual means not only obtaining a certain amount of

M'lumot, but also studying the methods of activity that are the result of IT (experience), that is, individual assimilation of it and thus the formation of social experience. The process of transferring knowledge, skills and qualifications to perform various types of activities, that is, the formation of important personal characteristics in a person and the pedagogical system that determines the process of this formation, is the subject of pedagogy [1].

The educational process, which is closely related to the material basis of the development of its society, has gone through several stages in its formation and development, the transformation of which is considered in addition to the educational system and is associated with a combination of internal factors. The most important of them are the level of development of industrial production, the dominant economic system, the level of development of pedagogical science and the dominant educational paradigm, the goal of Education, which is understood as "an individual society, country, self-consciously determined expectations, and the state seeks to achieve in the present and near future using the existing educational system" [2. p. 38].

Historically, in different periods, the goal of Education has been set in different proportions by a person, society and the state, personally prepared according to the level of development of productive forces and production relations in the country, the economic basis, production relations, and now the political system and a number of other factors are put in it [3].

The strategy for achieving the educational goal proposed by society to the student through state and public educational structures is an educational paradigm, "its implementation requires the creation of an appropriate educational space, which is carried out with the inclusion of the educational process, with the help and guidance of other individuals, with the exception of the educational environment, which [4].

RESULTS

Currently, the practical technology for implementing the existing educational paradigm in higher education is assigned to pedagogical concept, which is defined as follows:

a system of views on the relationship of processes and phenomena and concepts in Nature, Society from the point of view of a scientist;

m'lum a method of interpretation, understanding phenomena, processes, m'lum a view of the generality of phenomena, a leading idea for their systematic illumination ... leading idea in the structure of the theory [5];

historical conditioned, scientific knowledge and actualized by the progress of society, ideas about the phenomenon under study, views, system of basic ideas;

"The concept is a set of basic rules that fully and comprehensively reveal the essence, content and characteristics of the studied phenomenon, its existence in reality or in the practical activities of a person" [6];

the basic idea of research, or M'lum, is a form of presentation of research results that have a theoretical design and a well-defined logical structure [7].

Given the peculiarities of pedagogy as a science, the pedagogical concept is understood as follows:

the strategy of pedagogical activity, which forms the basis of relevant theories;

a system of generalized rules or views on understanding the essence, content, methodology and organization of the educational process, as well as the features of the activities of teachers and listeners in the process of its implementation;

"A complex, purposeful, dynamic fundamental knowledge system that fully and comprehensively reveals its essence, content, features of the pedagogical phenomenon, as well as the technology of working with it in modern educational conditions" [8].

The analysis of the T'rifs of the pedagogical category "pedagogical concept" makes it possible to identify the general, most important features of scientific pedagogical concept and, accordingly, its main components:

- the presence of a basic idea that reflects the author's position on the problem under consideration;

- its validity, its reliance on general scientific rules, the conditionality of the concept with the development of scientific knowledge in the fields of pedagogical science and related knowledge;

- consistency of rules and conclusions, relationship with M'lum and proven methods;

- approval of theoretical rules with the results of practical verification, which makes it possible to determine the structure and functions of the pedagogical concept on the basis of the construction methodology of concepts and the methodology of pedagogy.

In pedagogical concept "...two functions are combined-scientific-theoretical and constructive-technical (normative, regulatory)" [9, p. 73]. Accordingly, the main components of the pedagogical concept together determine the implementation of both scientific-theoretical and constructive-technical functions of the organization of the educational process, while in relation to the topic of scientific research, study is carried out at the E-Learning.

For a detailed consideration of the pedagogical concept of the organization of digital education in higher educational institutions, we distinguish the following components in the structure of the pedagogical concept:

-Value-target reference module, which reveals the socio-cultural aspect of the proposed pedagogical concept of the organization of digital education in higher educational institutions, which includes the main idea, purpose, values, conceptual and categorical apparatus of learning;

- a module of theoretical and meaningful content, the theoretical rules of which include methodological approaches used as sources and components of the main idea of the pedagogical concept of the organization of digital education in higher educational institutions;

- certain pedagogical laws and basic principles of the organization of the educational process in educational institutions of different levels, as well as popular pedagogical models and pedagogical technologies that ensure the achievement of the set pedagogical Goal, revealing logical and gnoseological data in a cumulative manner;

- Aspect of the proposed pedagogical concept of the organization of digital education in higher educational institutions;

- the proposed pedagogical model of the process under consideration, its regulatory, technical and technological components, which together provide a practical aspect of the proposed pedagogical concept of the organization of digital education in higher educational institutions, "provides a general understanding of what the content and process of educational activities should be, how they should be implemented and changed, what should be" [9, p. 185].

The definition of pedagogical concept as a system of knowledge about a pedagogical phenomenon, combined with a leading idea, and in the relationship of socio-cultural (value-semantic interpretation), logical-gnoseological (objective meaning), practical (normative foundations) aspects, it is possible to realize a scientific-theoretical and constructive-technological function at all.

The following drawing 1 presents the structure of the pedagogical concept for the organization of digital education [10, p. 109].

DISCUSSION

A practical tool that allows you to implement methodological principles of scientific analysis of pedagogical phenomena, processes, phenomena is a methodological approach. I.V.Blauberg and E.G.The yudins define a methodological approach "as a fundamental methodological orientation of research, as a point of view that considers the object of study (the method of object identification)".

N.Stefanov describes the methodological approach as" a complex (system) of principles that determine the general purpose and strategy of relevant activities."

A.Yu.Petrov defines the pedagogical category "methodical approach" as having two M'no:

- first, the pedagogical category "methodical approach" is considered as the initial principle, the main position or belief that forms the basis of the research activity of the researcher;

- secondly, the pedagogical category "methodical approach" determines the direction of study of the object (subject) of research, determines the purpose of scientific research, its object and subject, its planned results.

The most general definition today is N.V.Ippolitova, giving, defines the methodological approach as a single triad: "a set of ideas that determine the general scientific worldview position of the scientist; principles that form the basis of the research strategy; methods, methods, procedures that ensure the implementation of the selected strategy in practice". [11, p. 12].

The complexity, versatility inherent in all phenomena of pedagogical reality their two-way relationship and interdependence the emergence, development of many methodological approaches that reflect the peculiarities of a particular field of Science in pedagogical science has led to their application in pedagogical practice.

The choice of a specific methodological approach from a set with an M'lum for conducting scientific research or from a set of specific methodological approaches is determined by the need to obtain objective, reliable scientific m'lumats that allow you to create a complete picture of the pedagogical phenomenon under study. The objectivity, accuracy and reliability of the results obtained directly depends on the choice of a specific methodological approach for conducting pedagogical research, the main conditions of which are as follows:

- the methodological approaches chosen by the researchers should be adequate, that is, fully consistent with the goals and objectives of pedagogical research;

- to obtain an objective and holistic picture of the pedagogical phenomenon under study, it is necessary to use not one, but several approaches corresponding to one or more levels of the methodology;

- the set of methodological approaches used in the study does not include mutually denying approaches;

The methodological approaches used in pedagogical research should complement each other, which makes it possible to study a specific object in every possible way and in all its relationships [11, p. 14].

As a methodological basis of the pedagogical concept of the organization of digital education in higher educational institutions, the Basic Rules of axiological, environmental, systemic, cultural, technological and information approaches are used.

The basic Terms, the formulas of the Basic Rules, the research postulates, as well as the connections between them that must be considered within the framework of the concept, make up its only conceptual and categorical apparatus.

The main concepts that provide scientific, methodological and technological provision of digital education in higher educational institutions are the following pedagogical categories: "virtual educational environment"; "pedagogical situation"; "educational situation"; "purpose of individual education"; "educational process", "individual educational trajectory of the student" – definitions are clarified and corrected in the process of learning [12].

The core of the concept includes the basic theoretical rules, laws and principles of the functioning of the studied process, recognized and approved in the practical activities of professors and teachers on the basis of the theoretical and methodological scientific foundations being applied. The formation of the core of pedagogical concept, based on the previously achieved theoretical developments and practical results, makes it possible to expand the understanding of the process Theoretically and practically, to determine the ways and directions of further development of the process [13].

Our study optimizes the core of the concept in terms of the logical-semantic model of the educational space and educational environment, time and other parameters that contribute to the effectiveness of the educational process, as well as the mathematical apparatus that determines the construction of the student's individual educational trajectory in the educational space of higher educational institutions.

CONCLUSION

The content and semantic content of the concept of the organization of digital education in higher educational institutions is a process put forward within the framework of the concept, the process under study, the reflection and implementation of theoretical rules carried out in the form of an object or model of its individual parts, aspects, as well as stages, levels, system of implementation, which allows

The content of the components of digital education in higher educational institutions as a pedagogical system includes promising individual goals of Education; conducting a prophetic pedagogical examination; means of communication; educational submissions; participation of the student, pedagogical and expert community as subjects of the educational process.

Pedagogical conditions for the effective functioning of digital education as a specific pedagogical process are a system of Specially Selected conditions, in which the achievement of the highest efficiency indicator of the studied process is ensured.

Examination of the concept allows you to empirically test its Basic Rules.

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